

LEISURE TIME ACTIVITIES AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE AGED 13-16 FROM KOSOVO, BULGARIA AND POLAND

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Abstract

This paper presents the results of the research on the physical activity of school youth in three European countries (Poland, Bulgaria, Kosovo) which are at different stages of socio-economic development and, therefore, of different possibilities and conditions in terms of leisure and mobility.

The purpose of this cognitive study was to diagnose certain aspects of the lifestyle of young people aged 13-16 from Kosovo, Bulgaria and Poland, with a particular focus on physical activity. The practical aim, however, was an indication of such actions, arising from past experience that would aim at improving lifestyle, and could lead to the elimination or prevention of certain causes of physical inactivity by the youth of the countries surveyed.

The research was conducted by the use of a diagnostic survey of a group of 524 people aged 13-16, among whom there were 88 people from Bulgaria, 136 people from Poland and 300 people from Kosovo. The research material was collected in 2012.

The research that was carried out shows that the level of wealth (not so much of the family, but of the specific country) may have an impact on the choice of activities chosen by the youth. Undoubtedly socio-cultural factors and the tradition of social life, which impose certain ways of spending leisure time (as can be seen particularly in the case of the Bulgarian and Kosovar youth) are also of great importance. The above observations, taking into account local conditions, should be the starting point for all those who plan to introduce changes in the physical education systems in each of these countries in the future.

Key words: *lifestyle, youth, physical activity, socio-cultural factors, Poland, Bulgaria, Kosovo.*

Introduction

With adolescents aged 13-16 their interests and expectations are the subjects to transformation. Young people at this age often cause problems, are difficult to communicate with, there may also occur the phenomenon of "youthful rebellion". During this period you can also see that the physical activity in their leisure time, to a large extent, will depend on a number of activities, which go beyond the team problems covered by school curriculum but deals with educational environment in which each student grows up. The development of interests takes place in various sections, clubs, interests, and circles. From the point of view of health needs, the most important part of this activity should be based on physical activities. It is known that such activities have a very positive impact on the

development of biological characteristics (stimulate growth, strengthen the body, develop speed, stamina, concentration, improve reflex) [10], and psychosocial problems (self-esteem, the ability to self-control, the ability to work with other people).

For the sake of clarity, first the term of leisure requires clarification. For the first time it was defined during an international conference held in 1956. As defined by the French sociologist Dumazedier [4], leisure means all the activities taken by an individual for entertainment or self-development, voluntary participation in social life out of social and family responsibilities. This definition considers only adults. In turn, according to Dąbrowski [3] leisure time of young people is the time, which remains to their own disposal after fulfilling their body's needs and completing the duties at home and school, in

which they can conduct their activities in agreement with their tastes, related to leisure, entertainment and satisfying their own interests.

To get a fuller picture of youth's behavior in critical social, psychological and physical period of growing up, research study have been carried out in three societies (Poland, Bulgaria, Kosovo) of different degrees of political, economic and socio-cultural development. In pedagogy such comparative studies are conducted in order to identify possible trends and development paths. The first step is to identify the current state of things.

Aims of the research

The cognitive objective [2] of the present study was to diagnose certain aspects of the lifestyle of young people aged 13-16 from Kosovo, Bulgaria and Poland, with particular focus on physical activity. The practical aim was an indication of such actions, arising from past experience that would improve lifestyle, and could lead to the elimination or prevention of certain causes of not making movement activity by the youth of the countries surveyed.

Material and method

The research material was collected in the course of the surveys. A research tool used to evaluate the lifestyle of students was a questionnaire "My lifestyle", developed by a team of European researchers [Telama R., Naul R., Nupponen H., Rychtecky A., Vuolle P., 2002] for the project and translated into Polish by the research team from University School of Physical Education. The research was conducted in the group of 524 people aged 13-16, among whom there were 88 people from Bulgaria - 35 girls (39,8%) and 53 boys (60,2%), 136 people from Poland - 49 girls (36,0%) and 87 boys (63,0%),

300 people from Kosovo - 152 girls (50,7%) and 148 boys (49,3%). The research material was collected in 2012 during the implementation of the two projects. The first project, is the Polish part of the European research project "Olympism and the integration of young people through education" (no 2010-1-PL 1-COM13-115641) under the scheme "Learning throughout life" - Comenius Regio Partnerships. The other project, during which the research material was collected, is the project "Post-Graduate Level Training of Trainers Programme in Physical Education and Sport" (no Europe Aid/130886/C/SER/KOS).

To determine the strength of the relationship between variable non-parametric test chi was used. Significance level $p < 0,05$ was accepted.

Results

Table 1 show the way on spending leisure time of young people. Frequently provided response was *listening to music*. This considers both students from Kosovo (girls 60,5%, boys 65,5%), Bulgaria (girls 71,4%, boys 45,3%), and Poland (girls 73,47%, boys 56,3%).

Other activities taken mostly in leisure time include *watching television, video* (girls from Kosovo 50,0%, boys from Poland 46,0%), *meeting friends* (girls from Bulgaria 60,0%, boys from Bulgaria 53,0%, Polish girls 63,3%) and *playing computer games* (boys from Bulgaria 57,0%, boys from Poland 49,4%). No student from Kosovo answered *I go to the disco*. A small percentage of the students pointed to the need to *visit family in spare time* - the largest percentage among the Bulgarian students (boys 16,4%, girls 11,0%).

Tab.1. Distribution of responses of students aged 13-15 to the question : "How do you spend your free time?". [%]

Leisure activities	KOSOVO		BULGARIA		POLAND	
	GIRLS	BOYS	GIRLS	BOYS	GIRLS	BOYS
a) listen to music	60,5	65,5	71,4	45,3	73,4	56,3
b) play instruments, sing in a choir, etc.	15,8	6,1	0,0	6,0	2,04	7,0
c) watch TV, video	50,0	26,0	34,3	38,0	30,61	46,0
d) meet friends	17,8	29,7	60,0	53,0	63,3	36,0
e) play cards or board games	2,6	4,0	6,0	17,0	2,04	1,1
f) play computer	10,5	16,2	40,0	57,0	24,5	49,4

g) read books, magazines	31,0	24,3	0,0	7,5	18,4	6,0
h) do sport in a club or sports section	29,0	35,1	14,3	23,0	34,7	40,2
i) do sport individually	14,5	36,0	11,4	13,2	4,08	18,4
j) attend sports events	20,0	3,4	0,0	7,5	8,2	13,0
k) go to discos	0,0	0,0	8,6	7,5	4,1	9,2
l) go to the cinema, theatre, concerts	22,0	10,1	26,0	4,0	12,2	3,4
m) spend time on hobbies	5,0	9,5	20,0	9,4	12,2	7,0
n) visit family	16,4	11,0	6,0	4,0	4,1	0,0
o) do nothing	2,0	2,0	3,0	0,0	8,2	2,3
p) play with peers	6,0	8,1	11,4	2,0	0,0	5,0
q) others	3,3	19,0	6,0	7,5	0,0	0,0

Answers do not sum up to 100% because respondents could choose three answers.

Table 2 concerned physical activity taken up in leisure time (which lasted at least 30 minutes) in the past three months. Three frequency categories were taken into consideration: category I – *never or less than once a week*, category II - *once a week, twice a week, three times a week*, category III - *five times a week, every day*. Girls from Kosovo

(48,7%), Bulgaria (57,2%) and boys from Kosovo (46,7%) take physical activities *once to three times a week*. Students from Poland (boys 66,7% , girls 57,1%) and boys from Bulgaria (43,4%) take such an activity *daily and five times a week*. The differences in the responses vary at the significance level $p > 0,05$.

Tab.2. Number and percentage distribution of responses to the question "How often, over the past 3 months, did you take up motor activity in your free time? (lasting at least 30 minutes)."

Frequency of taking motor activity	BOYS						GIRLS					
	Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria		Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
a) never or less than once a week	44	29,7	5	5,7	12	22,6	73	48,0	4	8,2	4	11,4
b) 1-3 times a week	69	46,7	24	27,6	18	34,0	74	48,7	17	34,7	20	57,2
c) 5-7 times a week	35	23,6	58	66,7	23	43,4	5	3,3	28	57,1	11	31,4
Chi square	Chi ² = 45,78 p < 0,05						Chi ² = 87,11 p < 0,05					

In the next table are presented (Tab.3) the forms of physical activity taken in leisure time most often were presented. To those that are taken *often* by the surveyed boys belong: soccer (35,1% of the boys from Kosovo, 72,4% of the boys from Poland) and running (41,5% of the

boys from Bulgaria). Among the forms of physical activity that are *never* taken by the boys of Kosovo we can find speed skating (95,3%). In turn, the boys from Bulgaria (87,9%) and Poland (66,7%) *never* take the form of physical activity such as snowboarding.

Tab.3. Distribution of responses of boys aged 13-15 to the question: "In which forms of leisure-time physical activity do you participate?".

Forms of motor activity	Frequency of taking various forms of physical activity by boys in %								
	Never			Rarely			Often		
	KOS	BUL	POL	KOS	BUL	POL	KOS	BUL	POL
a) running	12,8	15,0	11,5	49,3	43,4	37,9	35,1	41,5	50,6
b) swimming	20,9	45,2	17,2	75,7	43,4	45,9	3,4	11,3	36,8
c) cycling	47,9	35,8	6,9	34,45	30,1	35,6	17,6	33,9	57,5
d) roller-skating	85,8	75,4	55,2	12,2	16,9	28,7	2,0	7,5	16,1
e) basketball	28,4	56,6	16,1	58,1	33,9	52,9	13,5	9,4	27,6
f) volleyball	19,6	30,1	28,7	50,7	39,6	49,4	29,7	7,5	21,8

g) football	21,6	43,4	10,3	37,8	22,6	17,2	40,5	33,9	72,4
h) handball	65,5	71,7	31,0	29,7	18,8	39,1	4,7	9,4	29,9
i) aerobics	81,8	83,0	59,8	13,5	7,5	26,4	4,7	9,4	13,8
j) gym	83,1	58,4	32,2	12,2	28,3	40,2	4,7	13,2	27,6
k) skateboarding	86,5	73,5	63,2	6,8	20,7	26,4	6,8	5,6	10,3
l) skating	95,3	66,0	50,6	4,0	26,4	36,8	0,7	7,5	12,6
m) skiing	39,2	69,8	60,9	56,8	18,8	28,7	4,0	11,3	10,3
n) snowboarding	72,9	87,9	66,7	22,9	9,4	23,0	4,0	5,6	10,3
p) gymnastics	44,6	64,1	36,8	46,6	22,6	35,6	8,8	13,2	27,6
q) martial arts	65,5	83,0	63,2	26,3	13,2	10,3	8,1	3,7	26,4
r) others	0,0	54,7	58,6	0,0	18,8	16,1	0,0	28,3	25,3

Respondents could choose three answers. The results do not sum up to 100%.

Among girls taking various forms of physical activity is as follows (Tab.4). Forms of physical activity chosen *often* in leisure time: volleyball (16,4% of girls from Kosovo) and cycling (40% of girls from Bulgaria, 44,9% of the girls from Poland). Among girls from Kosovo a form of

physical activity which is *never* taken is speed skating (97,4%). Girls from Bulgaria *never* participate in the aerobics (97,1%). When it comes to Polish girls, they *never* practice martial arts.

Tab. 4. Distribution of girls' responses to the question: "In which forms of leisure time physical activity do you participate?"

Frequency of taking various forms of physical activity by girls in %									
Forms of physical activity	Never			Rarely			Often		
	KOS	BUL	POL	KOS	BUL	POL	KOS	BUL	POL
a) running	34,2	5,7	8,2	57,2	65,7	59,2	7,2	28,6	32,6
b) swimming	19,1	31,4	22,4	80,9	54,3	44,9	0,0	14,3	32,6
c) cycling	61,8	22,8	4,1	30,3	37,1	51,0	7,9	40,0	44,9
d) roller-skating	94,7	71,4	36,7	5,3	25,7	36,7	0,0	2,9	42,9
e) basketball	59,2	54,3	32,6	36,2	42,9	48,9	4,6	2,9	18,4
f) volleyball	25,0	31,4	18,4	58,5	57,1	46,9	16,4	11,4	34,7
g) football	63,2	48,6	36,7	25,0	22,9	36,7	11,8	28,6	26,5
h) handball	88,2	74,3	53,1	9,2	17,1	38,8	2,6	8,6	8,2
i) aerobics	71,7	97,1	48,9	25,7	2,9	36,7	2,6	0,0	14,9
j) gym	94,7	51,4	59,2	3,3	37,1	26,5	1,9	11,4	14,9
k) skateboarding	96,0	65,6	65,3	0,0	28,6	22,4	3,9	2,9	12,2
l) skating	97,4	62,9	42,9	2,6	31,4	40,8	0,0	5,7	16,3
m) skiing	53,4	74,3	53,1	45,4	14,3	32,6	2,6	11,4	14,3
n) snowboarding	88,8	94,3	63,3	10,5	2,9	22,4	0,7	2,9	14,3
p) gymnastics	65,1	68,6	34,7	31,6	22,9	30,6	3,3	8,6	34,7
q) martial arts	76,3	65,7	73,5	18,4	25,7	0,0	5,3	8,6	26,5
r) others	0,0	28,6	51,0	0,0	28,6	18,4	0,0	14,3	30,6

Respondents could choose three answers. The results do not sum up to 100%.

Table 5 shows the motivation to participate in physical activities. Respondents had the option of choosing three of the 13 responses given. The factor that motivates the surveyed most to participate in a variety of physical activities is the desire to *be in good physical condition* (45,3% of the boys from Kosovo, 63,3% of girls from Poland, 55,2% of boys from Poland, 57,1% of girls from Bulgaria, 67,9% boys

from Bulgaria). Quite often there were also answers: *an opportunity to meet new people* (54,6% of girls from Kosovo), *for relaxation* (59,9% of the girls from Kosovo), *desire to make sports career* (56,3% of boys from Poland), *for fun* (57,1% of girls from Bulgaria) and *for one's own health* (57,1% of girls from Bulgaria).

Tab.5. Distribution of responses to the question: "I participate in a variety of motor activities because: . . ." [%]

Motives to take motor activity in free time	KOSOVO		POLAND		BULGARIA	
	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys
a) want to make a sports career	26,3	38,5	28,6	56,3	8,5	18,9
b) this is an opportunity to make new friends	54,6	30,4	20,4	12,6	17,1	9,4
c) like competing	15,8	35,1	10,2	19,5	20,0	35,8
d) want to be in good shape	24,3	45,3	63,3	55,2	57,1	67,9
e) this is relaxation for me	59,9	37,8	24,5	18,4	14,2	3,8
f) for health	25,7	33,1	44,9	36,8	57,1	58,5
g) to gain nice appearance	25,7	2,0	26,5	17,2	25,7	18,9
h) want to get a better mark in PE	9,2	10,8	8,2	4,6	14,2	15,1
i) this is an opportunity to meet friends	26,3	15,5	22,4	9,2	8,5	1,9
j) for fun	25,7	22,3	14,3	11,5	57,1	30,2
k) can realize in sport	3,3	10,1	18,4	13,8	2,8	16,9
l) I'm encouraged by friends and siblings	0,0	0,0	0,0	2,3	0,0	3,8
m) to gain material profits	0,7	10,1	0,0	12,6	0,0	1,9

Respondents could choose three answers. The results do not sum up to 100%.

Table 6 present with whom respondents take physical activities in their leisure time and they had five options to choose from. The vast majority of the respondents from all the three

countries replied that they take movement activities in their leisure time *with her friends*. The differences in the responses vary at the significance level $p < 0,05$.

Tab. 6. The distribution of responses to the question: I take motor activities in my free time mostly with..."

I take motor activities most often with...	Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria		Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria	
	BOYS		BOYS		BOYS		GIRLS		GIRLS		GIRLS	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
a) with parents	8	5,4	6	6,9	6	11,3	20	13,2	3	6,1	1	2,9
b) with siblings	20	13,5	2	2,3	3	5,7	40	26,3	1	2,0	2	5,7
c) with friends	114	77,0	61	70,1	34	64,1	83	54,6	38	77,6	25	71,4
d) on my own	3	2,0	14	16,1	6	11,3	9	5,9	7	14,3	5	14,3
e) with other persons	3	20,3	4	4,6	4	7,6	0	0,0	0	0,0	2	5,7
Chi square	Chi ² = 29,37 p < 0,05						Chi ² =37,27 p < 0,05					

Table 7 concern the evaluation of one's health condition, where respondents had five options to choose from. With the exception of the boys from Poland (46,0%), who described their

health condition as very healthy, the rest of the surveyed evaluated their health condition as *healthy*. The differences in the responses of the surveyed were statistically significant ($p < 0,05$).

Tab. 7. The distribution of responses to the question: "I believe I am... "

I believe I am	Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria		Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria	
	BOYS		BOYS		BOYS		GIRLS		GIRLS		GIRLS	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
a) very healthy	43	29,1	40	46	20	37,7	15	9,8	12	24,5	10	28,6
b) healthy	93	62,8	29	33,3	23	43,4	98	64,5	25	51,0	22	62,9
c) ill	1	0,7	5	5,7	2	3,8	0	0,0	0	0,0	1	2,8
d) cannot evaluate my health condition	11	7,4	13	15,0	8	15,1	39	25,7	12	24,5	2	5,7
Chi square	Chi ² = 23,57 p < 0,05						Chi ² = 20,56 p < 0,05					

Respondents were asked also to assess their physical condition. Table 8 show the results. The boys from Poland (39,1%), girls from Poland (40,8%) and girls from Bulgaria (34,3%) appreciated their agility as *very good*. However,

the boys from Kosovo (42,6%), the boys from Bulgaria (43,4%) and girls from Kosovo (update to reach 44,7%) rated their physical condition as *good*. The differences in responses were statistically significant. (p<0,05)

Tab. 8. Distribution of responses to the question: " I evaluate my physical condition as..."

My motor skills evaluate as...	Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria		Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria	
	BOYS		BOYS		BOYS		GIRLS		GIRLS		GIRLS	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
a) outstanding	18	12,2	28	32,2	6	11,3	8	5,3	8	16,3	3	8,6
b) very good	61	41,2	34	39,1	16	30,2	56	36,8	20	40,8	12	34,3
c) good	63	42,6	22	25,3	23	43,4	68	44,7	14	28,6	11	31,4
d) sufficient	6	4,0	1	1,1	6	11,3	20	13,2	6	12,3	7	20,0
e) poor	0	0,0	2	2,3	2	3,8	0	0,0	1	2,0	2	5,7
Chi square	Chi ² =30,38 p < 0,05						Chi ² =15,77 p < 0,05					

Tab. 9a. Distribution of answers to the question: "Do your parents participate in various forms of motor activity?" (information about the mother and father)

Motor activity taken up by mother	Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria		Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria	
	BOYS		BOYS		BOYS		GIRLS		GIRLS		GIRLS	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
a) doesn't take up	69	46,6	23	26,5	19	35,9	96	63,2	11	22,5	10	28,6
b) takes up occasionally	54	36,5	37	42,5	17	32,0	49	32,2	25	51,0	16	45,7
c) takes up regularly	13	8,8	17	19,5	4	7,6	6	3,9	6	12,2	4	11,4
d) do not know	12	8,1	10	11,5	13	24,5	1	0,7	7	14,3	5	14,3
Chi square	Chi ² =22,03 p < 0,05						Chi ² =43,40 p < 0,05					

Tab. 9b. Distribution of answers to the question: "Do your parents participate in various forms of motor activity?" (information about the mother and father)

Motor activity taken up by father	Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria		Kosovo		Poland		Bulgaria	
	BOYS		BOYS		BOYS		GIRLS		GIRLS		GIRLS	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
a) doesn't take up	45	30,4	14	16,1	18	34,0	26	17,1	9	18,4	8	22,9
b) takes up occasionally	43	29,1	32	36,8	17	32,1	67	44,1	21	42,8	13	37,1
c) takes up regularly	50	33,8	22	25,3	4	7,5	58	38,2	10	20,4	5	14,3
d) do not know	10	6,8	19	21,8	14	26,4	1	0,6	9	18,4	9	25,7
Chi square	Chi ² =242,12 p < 0,05						Chi ² =74,09 p < 0,05					

The last table (Tab.9) presents results of responses about the taking up by the parents of the respondents different forms of physical activity (separate mother and father). Mothers of the young from Kosovo (girls 63,2%, boys 46,6%) and of the boys from Bulgaria (35,9%) have been assessed as persons not taking the activity, while the students in Poland (girls 51,0%, boys 42,5%) and girls from Bulgaria (45,7%) assessed their mothers as persons sometimes choosing physical activity. The differences in the responses vary at the significance level $p < 0,05$.

In turn, fathers were judged by the majority as sometimes taking physical activity (the boys from Poland 36,8%, girls from Kosovo 44,1%, from Poland 42,8% and Bulgaria 37,1%). On the other hand, boys from Bulgaria (34,0%) see their fathers as persons not taking physical activity, but the boys from Kosovo (33,8%) consider their fathers as persons regularly taking physical activity. The differences in the responses vary at the significance level $p < 0,05$.

Discussion and Conclusion

Leisure time is one of the major social problems. It is getting more difficult for the youth to resist the temptation of spending their leisure time in the form of passively, sedentary behaviours in a situation when on the market there are available attractive multimedia devices and companies compete in "gluing" their customers not only to the product but also to chairs or sofas. It's creates "couch potato"

generation. Therefore, a very important aspect is providing a good model to imitate by parents, teachers and education.

The educational system steps into man's life in the period of its greatest spiritual and physical plasticity when one's lifestyle is created. According to Nowak-Starz [6]: "lifestyle is the image of the individual's and/or group's functioning." The process of forming a given lifestyle runs parallel to educational activity. A very important point is the period of adolescence. The lifestyle of an individual can strengthen his/her health potential or quite the opposite can cause deterioration. That is why we can talk about its pro-health or anti-health character.

The information collected in the course of our research has made it possible to specify the leisure time, the frequency of the physical activity of the enterprise, participation in various activities, and physical activity it's taken by parents of students.

Comparing the results of the studies concerning the declared by the students physical activity taken in their leisure time, as optimistic should be considered the fact that the majority of respondents declared taking physical activity *once to three times a week*. Such a response was given by the girls from Kosovo (48,7%), girls from Bulgaria (57,2%), the boys from Kosovo (46,7%). *Five times a week and more*, declared Polish students - boys (66,7%), girls (57,1%) and the boys from Bulgaria (43,4%). Definitely a smaller percentage of responses in the first

category was *not at all, or less than once a week*.

Obtained results indicate that the factors encouraging the surveyed to physical activity are: relaxation, good physical condition, the benefits for health, the desire to have fun and sports career. What's interesting for girls at this age getting a nice appearance is not the most motivating factor. The girls as a motivator enumerated: the desire to be in good physical condition, their health, an opportunity to meet new people, and the desire to have fun. From a study carried out by Kurzak and Pawelec [5] among middle school students in Warsaw, it appears that the Warsaw lower-secondary school students daily and at the weekends prefer sedentary lifestyle. This may result from the declared interest in serials and computer games. The way of spending weekends may reflect the lifestyle of modern families. The most common weekend pass-time preferences are connected with meetings friends and family. Leisure habits associated with physical activity are characteristic only to the fourth lower-secondary school student in Warsaw.

The results of the research correspond to the results of the studies carried out among young people by Skawiński et al. [9], who pointed out that young people spend most of their leisure time in front of the computer or TV. Similar conclusions also drew Oblecińska and Woynarowska [7] in large population studies. Also, according to a study carried out by Bajurna et al. [1] in Poland activities for lower-secondary school students are mainly various forms of physical activity, but also thematic activities. In these tests, the motor activity of youth was rated as moderate. The results of the research indicate that most frequently taken forms of spending leisure time by young people in all the countries surveyed are listening to music, meeting friends, playing computer and watching TV, video.

When analyzing the results of the research the differences in the responses mainly between the young people of Kosovo and their peers from Bulgaria and Poland were emphasized. The differences observed may be the result of differences in educational systems, as well as differences in terms of cultural, social and economic context.

The obvious reason for that may be the lack of access to such equipment or the lack of common access to the Internet. It must be assumed that further economic development will result in an increase in the percentage of young people choosing this form of leisure. Among the forms of activity never taken by lower-secondary school students from Kosovo there are: roller-skating, aerobics, skateboarding and skating, those forms can be classified as "expensive" (due to the need to have expensive sports equipment), and poorly available (fitness club, sports halls, skating rinks). None of the students from Kosovo indicated going to discos, which may result from cultural and religious differences. On the other hand, while a higher percentage of respondents among young people from Kosovo, when compared to Polish and Bulgarian peers, pointed out to reading books. Interestingly, also the youth of Kosovo in their free time are more likely to visit family, in comparison to children from Bulgaria and Poland.

Effectiveness of health education (and not only) requires compatibility between the health education realized at schools and what the student experiences in the family. A significant impact on the development of lifestyle and health behavior has a family. It has been shown that this support is beneficial as far as solidifying of good health habits is concerned. [12]. In the research, parents were asked if they take any activity (separately mothers and fathers). In the case of mothers, the answers were divided between *do not take and sometimes take*, which applies to all groups surveyed in each of the countries. In turn, in the case of the fathers physical activity, it was assessed better. Among the boys from Kosovo a large number of responses (33,8%) indicated that fathers *regularly practice* physical activity. In the case of boys from Poland, it was only 25,3% and 7,5% in Bulgaria.

This situation can be caused by different division of family duties and, in general, different perception of the traditional role of a man, the head of the family in the tested countries of so different socio-cultural and religious conditions.

The need for action for the health of young people is noted in the important international documents in which a lot of joint

recommendations are repeated on the need to improve the health care system, promote healthy lifestyles, improving life skills as a modern strategy for prevention of many disorders. An important idea is to enable young people to prioritize and build programs for the benefit of their health [11]. It seems that in some countries (Bulgaria, Kosovo) this is difficult to achieve at the present stage of the development of local education systems and often very authoritarian educational traditions. Even in Poland, which introduced democracy over two decades ago only recently the autonomy of teachers (1999), then successively of students (2009) was increased by introducing into the core curriculum the need to determine some solutions and educational plans together with students.

Bridging social inequality can contribute to the overall improvement of health of the public and selected age groups. The relationship between social factors and teenagers' health is

complex. Drawing conclusions on differences depends on accepted health and social factors. It is believed that during the period of adolescence health differences show not that strongly as in early childhood and during adulthood [8]. The reason for that is smaller influence of factors connected with family life, and bigger of those connected with a peer group. The research shows that the level of wealth (not so much of the family, but of the whole country) may have an impact on the choice of activities taken by the youth. Undoubtedly, socio-cultural factors and the tradition of social life also have great impact and impose certain ways of spending leisure time (as can be seen particularly in the case of the Bulgarian and Kosovar youth). The above observations, the future taking into account local conditions, should be a starting point for those planning changes in physical education systems in each of these countries.

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